

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE 2.1

Methodological approach for FARCLIMATE

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List of acronyms

EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
ID	Identity
IP	Intellectual Property
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLTRL	Living Lab Technology Readiness Level
R&D	Research & Development
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TIDieR	Template for intervention description and replication
WP	Work Package

Project information

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5	INVIABLE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L.	INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO	FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION	GCG
8	UNIVERSITE DE LIEGE	ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN	CESEFOR
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Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the Living Lab methodology that will be implemented by the FARCLIMATE regions and communities. The FARCLIMATE Project is funded by the European Commission Horizon Europe Programme **Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change**, the objective of which is to support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030. FARCLIMATE aims to enhance climate resilience in European regions and communities while addressing potential political, social, and economic challenges. As highlighted by the European Commission's EU strategy on adaptation to climate change adopted on 24th February 2021, the urgency to build resilience in the face of climate change is vital. FARCLIMATE will strengthen climate-change resilience across Europe through a twofold approach. Firstly, by implementing specific actions and transversal activities targeting at least 20 European regions and communities. Secondly, by providing a compilation of tools and recommendations to diverse stakeholders typically overlooked in climate change communication efforts.

The regions and communities will be empowered through Living Lab methodology, executing technical interventions in different economic sectors, and disseminating results using a knowledge-inspiring approach. FARCLIMATE targets both responsible and affected stakeholders of the quadruple helix, including regional and local governments, the private sector, civil society, social partners, academia, and industries, focusing on three key sectors impacted by climate change: agriculture, forestry, and fisheries. Living Labs will be established to facilitate co-creation, testing, and scaling-up of innovative activities in real-life environments. These Living Labs serve as open innovation ecosystems, employing a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation methodologies and activities within communities, placing citizens at the centre of the innovation process.

To ensure that the key components of Living Labs are implemented and developed, part of the wider FARCLIMATE training process will be focused on developments of Living Labs in the case studies and will be structured with the help of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas. This digital tool was developed by ENoLL to examine key structural and operational aspects of Living Labs and has been adapted to project needs. The canvas covers the following topics:

- Purpose of the Living Lab
- Vision and scope
- Host organisation
- Stakeholders
- Living Lab context
- People and Internal Roles
- Strategy
- SWOT
- Governance
- Value for the stakeholders
- Resources and sustainability
- Living Lab Communication Channels
- Monitoring and Evaluation

The deliverable also outlines the Living Lab research process, which aims to uncover new knowledge, insights, and understanding about the specific topics addressed by the Living Lab. In addition, a common activity in Living Labs across various Technology Readiness Levels is outlined. The goal is to emphasize the types of exploratory and confirmatory research objectives conducted at each stage and to outline the level of solution maturity. This framework will be used for tracking the evolution of the developed solutions of the FARCLIMATE Living Labs.

Moreover, the deliverable introduces the Living Lab Evaluation Framework. This framework is developed to evaluate the maturity levels of both existing Living Labs and those striving to achieve Living Lab status. The Evaluation framework is divided into 5 different sections:

- Strategy
- Operations
- Openness
- Users & Reality
- Impact & value
- Stability & harmonization

And finally, the Key Performance Indicators essential for evaluating Living Labs are outlined alongside each corresponding section. Overall, this document will provide FARCLIMATE Living Labs with a roadmap of steps to develop certifiable Living Labs.

1 Introduction

The past decade has marked a significant milestone in climate history, with temperatures soaring to unprecedented levels and breaking records on eight occasions. Despite efforts to curb greenhouse gas emissions, the world continues to grapple with the far-reaching impacts of climate change, which will continue for decades to come. Long-term repercussions of slow onset events such as desertification, deglaciation, biodiversity loss, land degradation, ocean acidification, and sea level rise pose ongoing threats to ecosystems and livelihoods worldwide. These cumulative impacts underscore the urgent need for concerted global action to address the complex challenges posed by climate change. Considering the climate challenges confronting European nations and to facilitate the dissemination of adaptation measures across the continent, the European Commission has proposed a Climate Change Adaptation Mission, one of the five EU missions tackling some of the greatest challenges facing our society today (European Commission, 2021).

This deliverable is written within the FARCLIMATE project, which is supported by funding from the Climate Change Adaptation Mission of the European Union. In particular, the Deliverable is an output of the Task 2.1 *Methodological approach to identify cases and its extent* which falls under Work Package 2 *Case studies development & Stakeholders interaction*. This Work Package seeks to provide the conceptual and operative basis to unlock the potential of adaptation to the climate change of the regions to tackle the challenges posed by climate change adaptation through an interdisciplinary, multisectoral, and multi-actor approach.

FARCLIMATE actions will be implemented in at least 20 regions and communities, designated as case studies, throughout Europe. These case studies will focus on developing transformative solutions to enhance climate resilience in the fisheries, forestry, and agriculture sectors. Additionally, the project aims to train these case studies in the Living Lab methodology, with the goal of establishing 20 Living Labs by the project's conclusion, with 9 of them achieving certification by ENoLL. FARCLIMATE will execute its case studies in two phases, adhering to the specifications outlined in Part B of the Grant Agreement. The initial phase, named the Proposal stage, will encompass a minimum of nine case studies, commencing their engagement by mid-2024. Subsequently, the Implementation stage, which follows as the second phase, will see an additional 11 case studies joining FARCLIMATE, starting around mid-2025. The selection of candidate regions and communities for FARCLIMATE case studies underwent thorough evaluation, as documented in deliverable D2.2 *Compilation of FARCLIMATE Case Studies*.

The FARCLIMATE project has outlined the following work program:

- Initial engagement with all relevant stakeholders in each region, establishing management mechanisms.
- Establishment of Living Labs to facilitate co-creation, testing, and scaling-up of innovative activities in real-life environments.
- Comprehensive research on the main value chains, socioeconomic and environmental characteristics, and existing economic sectors of all investigated regions and communities, utilizing monitored indicators.

- Implementation of cross-cutting actions to be carried out in all case studies, including tailored training activities aimed at empowering communities, targeting various stakeholders, and focusing on climate change and associated hazards and risks.
- Deployment of technically and socially viable innovative solutions in the agriculture, forestry, and fisheries economic sectors, with specific strategies to enhance their capacity to adapt to climate change impacts within their domains.
- The creation of different tools to spread the obtained learnings, such as policy recommendation, guidelines, management plans and the innovative Transformation Hub.

At the heart of the project lies co-creation, emphasizing the vital engagement of stakeholders from the project's start. This approach will lead to the development and execution of tailored Living Labs at the case study sites, actively involving stakeholders throughout the process.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows: it begins with a methodological overview of Living Labs in Chapter 1. In Chapter 2, the deliverable delves into stakeholder engagement and core users, with further exploration planned in Deliverable 2.3 *Stakeholder Management Strategy* which will be released in June 2024. In Chapter 4, the Living Lab research process for Case Studies is outlined and subsequently, readers are guided through the process of establishing a Living Lab using the Living Lab Mapping Canvas tool in Chapter 5. And finally, in Chapter 6 the Living Lab evaluation framework is presented with corresponding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Chapter 7 provides conclusion and reflections.

1.1 Relation to other activities

Task T2.1 *The methodological approach to identify cases and their extent*, is a key task in project closely related to the other Work Package (WP) 2 tasks. First, the Task 2.2 *Selection of case studies* provides the cases but also receives feedback from Task 2.1 that helped to inform case study candidates about the Living Lab methodology. Second, Task 2.3 *Stakeholder management strategy* directly addresses the stakeholder management strategy for the case studies, which should align with the approach of this deliverable in a Living Lab setting. Task 2.4 *Set up of the cases studies through living-lab methodology* oversees the implementation of the methodology outlined in the Task 2.1, which is the setting up of case studies through Living Lab methodology. Finally, the T2.1 methodology defines key indicators and the configuration of stakeholder interaction, establishing the setting for T2.5 *Fostering a transformative change to resilience environments*, aimed at determining potential strategies and solutions to deal with the environmental change for each case study.

T2.1 informs the following tasks, which later work in close collaboration with the implementation of Living Labs (T2.4 *Set up of the cases studies through living-lab methodology*):

- T1.5 *Gender transformative programming*, tasked with ensuring that all the project's activities and influence integrate and promote good practices that lead to gender transformation.
- The dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities, as well as the activities for connecting with other projects and initiatives in the EU Climate Adaptation Mission (WP8).

Case studies are the backbone of the FARCLIMATE project; as such, the Living Lab methodology of T2.1 and its implementation in T2.4 define the main driver for the different activities of the project.

Specifically, T2.1 establishes a great deal of the strategical context for the work program that FARCLIMATE has outlined:

- Initial engagement with all relevant stakeholders in each region, establishing management mechanisms (WP2).
- Establishment of Living Labs to facilitate co-creation, testing, and scaling-up of innovative activities in real-life environments (WP2).
- Comprehensive research on the main value chains, socioeconomic and environmental characteristics, and existing economic sectors of all investigated regions and communities, utilizing monitored indicators and focusing on their adaptation to climate change (WP3).
- Implementation of cross-cutting actions to be carried out in all case studies, including tailored training activities aimed at empowering communities, targeting various stakeholders, and focusing on climate change and associated hazards and risks (WP4).
- Deployment of technically and socially viable innovative solutions in the agriculture, forestry, and fisheries economic sectors, with specific strategies to enhance their capacity to adapt to climate change impacts within their domains (WP5).
- The creation of different tools to spread the obtained learnings, such as policy recommendation, guidelines and management plans (WP6); the innovative Transformation Hub (WP7); and the dissemination and communication activities and the synergies with other projects addressing the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change (WP8).
- The first steps in creating the European Climate-Resilient Communities' Network (WP6).

1.2 Timeline of the Case Studies

The timeline which the case studies will follow unfolds across two key steps:

1. **Geoprocessing of Data:** This initial phase involves the processing of data to inform subsequent decisions and actions.
2. **Selection of Case Studies and Engagement:** Following the geoprocessing phase, case studies are selected, and engagement with stakeholders begins.

The compilation of case studies occurs in two waves:

- **First Wave (Month 6):** The initial compilation of case studies is completed by Month 6 and reported in Deliverable D2.2, titled *Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v1*.
- **Second Wave (Month 18):** A subsequent compilation of case studies is finalized by Month 18 and reported in Deliverable 2.7, *Compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies v2*.

By Month 9, the stakeholder management strategy is defined and documented in Deliverable D2.3, *Stakeholder Management Strategy*.

Task 2.4 *Set up of the cases studies through living-lab methodology* coordinates the setup and management of the 20 case studies according to Living Lab methodology. A program outline

is prepared every 6 months and implemented through monthly activities. Once selected, each community undergoes a series of online group trainings to familiarize themselves with Living Lab principles and basic methods. Each Living Lab will have a profile and reference person tasked with collecting challenges and proposed solutions co-designed with community members.

The proposed development process includes the following steps:

- Road mapping for Living Lab strategy and vision, along with preliminary work on developing a business model.
- Supporting Living Lab core teams in executing planned activities across different innovation process stages.
- Continuous evaluation in 6-month rotation cycles to refine planned case activities and overall Living Lab strategy.
- Cross-fertilization of experiences between individual Living Labs to identify best practices and define harmonized and scalable procedures.
- Labelling evaluation at the project's end to verify Living Labs meet defined criteria, including finalization of business models and scalability planning beyond project completion.

Training modules and curriculum will be defined by Month 12 and reported in D4.1 *Training modules/curriculum and methodology*), with the online training platform developed by Month 20. Testing of training occurs between Months 13-24, and case studies are trained between Months 20-28 to 45, depending on the target audience. Additionally, the conceptual and methodological basis for the Living Labs will be finalized by Month 15, as outlined in Milestone 5.

2 Living Labs

2.1 What are Living Labs?

Living Labs serve as open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, employing a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation methodologies and activities in communities, with a focus on placing citizens at the heart of the innovation process (ENoLL, 2010).

A Living Lab embodies the user co-creation approach and denotes an entity where this approach is employed. Thus, when discussing "Living Lab," the focus is on the approach itself. Conversely, when referring to "A Living Lab," emphasis is placed on an organization where this approach serves as the primary operational methodology.

Figure 1: Living Lab definition

Methodologically, Living Labs are networks comprising diverse actors, resources, and activities that integrate user-centered research and open innovation (Leminen, S., Westerlund, M., & Nyström, A. G., 2012). From an infrastructure perspective, they serve as facilities facilitating experimentation and co-creation with users in real-life environments (Schuurman, 2015).

Living Labs operate as intermediaries among citizens, academia, industry, and governmental bodies. These four actors in society are known as the **Quadruple Helix Model (QHM)**.

Academia: A key player in knowledge creation, increasingly driving innovation for economic and cultural growth.

Industry: Leads technological and organizational innovation, collaborating with stakeholders to produce and distribute goods and services.

Government: Focuses on societal value creation through policies, supporting industry and academia in development efforts.

Citizens: Provides essential insights into needs and experiences, shifting the innovation focus towards social aspects for a more inclusive approach.

Figure 2: The Quadruple Helix Model (QHM). Source: (Finqueliévich, 2016)

Living Labs facilitate joint-value co-creation, rapid prototyping, and the scaling up of innovations and businesses (ENoLL, 2010). These ecosystems utilize iterative feedback mechanisms across the innovation lifecycle, operating as modern research tools adapted to contemporary needs. By fostering citizen participation in co-research endeavors, Living Labs function as authentic research infrastructures catering to both scientific and technological pursuits, with their categorization contingent upon the maturity stage of the innovations they engage with.

A Living Lab diverges from conventional laboratories **by operating within real-life settings and adopting a user-centric approach**. Its physical and/or organizational boundaries are delineated by purpose, scope, and context. Participants have the flexibility to define parameters such as scope, objectives, duration, actor involvement, participation levels, and boundaries. Thus, **a Living Laboratory could be established on a street**, within a residence, within an organization, or encompass an entire city or industry, contingent upon the project's requirements (ENoLL, 2022).

Living Labs are frequently mistaken for early testbeds. The primary distinction lies in their philosophy, which focuses on **elevating users from passive subjects merely observed during testing to active contributors engaged in co-creating and exploring emerging ideas, innovative concepts, and related artifacts**. Consequently, a Living Lab serves as an experiential environment analogous to the concept of experiential learning, immersing users in a creative social milieu to design and experience their envisioned future. Moreover, Living Labs may serve policymakers and citizens in designing, exploring, experiencing, and refining new policies and regulations within real-life settings to assess their potential impacts before implementation (ENoLL, 2022).

2.2 Typologies of Living Labs

Living Labs transfer experimentation from corporate R&D departments into real-world settings, involving users, partners, and other stakeholders in the co-creation process. According to the study by (Leminen, S., Westerlund, M., & Nyström, A. G., 2012) Living Labs can be categorized into four types of networks based on open innovation principles:

- Utilizer-driven
- Enabler-driven
- Provider-driven
- User-driven

Understanding the characteristics of each type of Living Lab enables stakeholders to discern the primary drivers of innovation, anticipate potential outcomes, and determine their roles in the "Living Lab". The FARCLIMATE Living Labs will aim to become User-driven.

Characteristic	Type of Living Labs			
	<i>Utilizer-driven</i>	<i>Enabler-driven</i>	<i>Provider-driven</i>	<i>User-driven</i>
Purpose	Strategic R&D activity with preset objectives	Strategy development through action	Operations development through increased knowledge	Problem solving by collaborative accomplishments
Organization	Network forms around an utilizer, who organizes action for rapid knowledge results	Network forms around a region (regional development) or a funded project (e.g., public funding)	Network forms around a provider organization(s)	Network initiated by users lacks formal coordination mechanisms
Action	Utilizer guides information collection from the users and promotes knowledge creation that supports the achievement of preset goals	Information is collected and used together and knowledge is co-created in the network	Information is collected for immediate or postponed use; new knowledge is based on the information that provider gets from the others	Information is not collected formally and builds upon users' interests; knowledge is utilized in the network to help the user community
Outcomes	New knowledge for product and business development	Guided strategy change into a preferred direction	New knowledge supporting operations development	Solutions to users' everyday-life problems
Lifespan	Short	Short/medium/long	Short/medium/long	Long

Figure 3: Characteristics of different type of Living Labs (Leminen et al, 2012)

In addition, it is important to distinguish between Living Lab research, Living Lab projects, and Living Lab constellations.

To facilitate better conceptualization, (Schuurman, 2015) devised a three-layer model comprising **a macro level**, where a Living Lab is a set of stakeholders that organized to foster innovation, **a meso level** featuring the methodological toolbox, innovation projects shared by the Living Labs, and **a micro level** encompassing various methodological research steps to follow in order to develop a specific project.

Therefore, Living Labs as Open Innovation ecosystems allow an interconnection among these three-layers. These converge at the meso-level, offering valuable insights for innovation development (ENoLL, 2010).

level	definition	Research paradigm
<i>macro</i>	Living Lab constellation consisting of organized stakeholders (PPP-partnership)	Open Innovation: knowledge transfers between organisations
<i>meso</i>	Living Lab innovation project	Open & User Innovation: real-life experimentation, active user involvement, multi-method and multi-stakeholder
<i>micro</i>	Living Lab methodology consisting of different research steps	User Innovation: user involvement & contribution for innovation

Figure 4: The three-layered Living Lab model (Schuurman, 2015)

2.3 Key characteristics of Living Labs

Although the Living Labs types, focus and areas of work can vary, according to ENoLL, the following elements tend to be core features in the innovation hubs:

Orchestration: the Living Lab operates as the orchestrator within the ecosystem to connect and partner up with relevant stakeholders.

Multi stakeholder participation: taking a holistic view on society, involving stakeholders from the quadruple helix model: government, academia, private sector, and citizens.

Active user involvement: a Living Lab involves relevant stakeholders 'actively' in all relevant activities, ensuring their feedback is captured and implemented throughout the whole lifecycle of the innovation.

Co-creation: in a Living Lab, values are co-created bottom-up not only for but also by all relevant stakeholders, ensuring a higher adoption rate by the end of the process.

Real-life setting: a Living Lab operates in the real-life setting of the end-users, infusing innovations into their real-life instead of moving the user to test sites to explore the innovations.

Multi method approach: each Living Lab activity is problem driven. Therefore, the methodological approach towards every individual activity will be selected based on the expected outcomes of the activity and the stakeholders who need to be involved.

2.4 Why Living Labs?

Living Labs establish a trustworthy environment perceived by all stakeholders as secure and impartial, fostering openness and contribution. Stakeholders recognize the value proposition for themselves as well as for the entire ecosystem.

As a principle Living Labs boost the active stakeholder participation in all phases of the development of a product or a service. By allowing collaboration among multiple actors, Living Labs also enhance **Co-creation**.

Co-creation take place when the ideas, resources, tools of different participants are integrated from the selection of a problem to be solved to the launching of the solution. The following Living Lab Integrative Process adapted from (Mastelic, 2019) shows the phases, specific activities, and stakeholder integration in a co-creative environment. It follows the design-thinking methodology where the co-creation follows the diverging and converging process through the phases of empathise, define, ideate, prototype and test. The Living Lab Integrative Process is recommended for the adoption at the meso and micro levels of the Living Lab operations.

*Adapted from Mastelic, 2019

Figure 5 Living Lab Integrative Process (ENoLL, 2022) adapted from (Mastelic, 2019)

Traditionally, particularly in technology projects, activities are structured as top-down experiments, with users often treated merely as factors rather than active participants. However, there is a growing acknowledgment that this approach requires adjustment, with users evolving into equal contributors and co-creators rather than passive subjects of study. The Living Lab methodology aims for mutually beneficial outcomes derived from the active involvement of all stakeholders right from the project's inception.

Drawing from the results of various projects such as (VITALISE¹ GA ID 101007990, oPEN Lab² GA ID 101037080, URBANOME³ GA ID 945391) among others, certain benefits of employing the Living Lab approach can be summarized:

- Co-Creating Innovation / Solutions
- Mastering the Value Chain of the Given Project
- Identifying Key Stakeholders
- Understanding the Business of Key Stakeholders
- Recognizing the Value Created for The Stakeholders
- Developing Management Capabilities to Create Value for The Stakeholders
- Providing Strategic Intelligence to Guide Stakeholders into Value Creation
- Knowledge Transfer to Improve Value for Stakeholder

Examples of some practical benefits (ENoLL, 2010)

Figure 6: Examples of some practical benefits (ENoLL, 2010)

¹ <https://vitalise-project.eu/>

² <https://openlab-project.eu/>

³ <https://www.urbanome.eu/>

2.5 What real-life experimentation in a Living Lab entails?

Real-life experimentation is a key requirement for Living Labs as it enables deeper insights in the potential success of innovations.

Reassuring real-life setup within a Living Lab project is essential to provide the most reliable feedback from the users. The idea is, to mimic the original environment and circumstances at the venue where the experimentations are carried out. In case the venue is built, it is of utmost importance to have thorough planning and a deep understanding of the real venue's or life situations' overall behaviour and parameters as the setup cost can be significant. To be worthwhile the investment, the least post-productions are aimed.

Living Lab projects in Business-to-Business (B2B) innovation projects have some limitations however for reassuring real-life experimentation.

The technological complexity, the need for integration, and the difficulty in identifying testers have been identified as barriers and potential solutions have been suggested by the following study: *Overcoming Barriers to Experimentation in Business-to-Business Living Labs* (D'Hauwers, 2017).

2.6 Living Lab value

Living Labs are increasingly recognized for their significant value, as evidenced by a 2023 study (Santonen, T. et al, 2023), which evaluated 209 value proposition suggestions with input from 22 experts. This study addresses previous debates surrounding the perceived value of Living Labs, aiming to identify key elements of their value proposition based on expert opinions. Through an online workshop involving 22 experts, participants generated value propositions tailored to different customer groups within Living Labs, including researchers, policymakers, public authorities, and SMEs/companies, across various phases of the innovation process. These suggestions, rooted in the core activities of Living Labs, led to an initial categorization of their value propositions. Subsequently, expert insights informed a literature review that defined quantifiable value proposition elements.

Economic benefits

Economic benefits are gains that can be expressed in financial terms. The example from (Health Innovation Center of Southern Denmark, 2017) demonstrates that companies or academic institutions offer monetary compensations to conduct Living Lab research. In addition, Living Labs can be valuable for start-ups which are trying to reach their first customers and convince investors. In this case, Living Labs can aid in verifying customer acceptance and solution benefits to convince investors.

Improved innovation

Living Labs help improve the product or solution, whether it is a product, service, process, decision, or a policy. Through the Living Lab approach, the design and user experience quality can be improved (De Moor et al., 2010). Living Labs have been shown to facilitate better decision making and policy making when dealing with complex societal challenges (Barata, F.T. et al, 2017).

Validity and reliability

Living Lab research, which is driven by design-thinking, as demonstrated in the Living Lab integrative process shown in Figure 5, ensures better validity and reliability of results. With the combination of field work, close connection with the end users and combination of the multi method approach, the findings respond to the needs of a larger group of end-users.

Benefits for users and society

By involving end-users in the development activities, the products or services are more likely to benefit the end-users for which these solutions were developed.

Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities

Living Labs employ a multi-method approach that fosters collaboration among diverse stakeholders. This approach not only enhances transparency but also cultivates trust, crucial for effective collaboration. By bringing together stakeholders from different quadruple helix stakeholder groups, Living Labs facilitate exchanges on shared topics, enabling mutual learning on needs and constraints.

Safe environment for RDI

This entails establishing mechanisms to guarantee regulatory and legal compliance. Living Labs offer structures that safeguard stakeholders' rights and integrate ethical considerations into research.

Increased skills and capabilities

Living Labs can effectively transfer their accumulated knowledge and experience to end users through active engagement activities.

3 Core User Personas

Living Lab stakeholders encompass both Living Lab customers (individuals or organizations purchasing or utilizing Living Lab research infrastructure services for specific contract-based research) and end-users, who participate voluntarily in research after providing informed consent (Vervoort, K. et al, 2023). In this chapter we will focus on end-users who participate in the Living Lab engagement processes. The FARCLIMATE project aims to engage at least 600 stakeholders across the 20 regions through the established Living Labs. Stakeholder engagement is central to the project, ensuring their involvement from the project's inception to ensure adherence to the Living Lab methodology. However, identifying these stakeholders is a collaborative process that will unfold throughout the project duration. While the exact stakeholders may not be known at this stage, we will collectively define them with the case studies as the project progresses.

Quadruple helix stakeholder engagement is integral to the Living Lab methodology, as outlined in Chapter 2 and will be further defined within T2.3 on Stakeholder engagement. Living Labs adopt a systematic user co-creation approach, placing citizens at the forefront of the innovation process.

This systematic approach entails meticulous planning of the co-creation process, ensuring that it is not left to chance but rather carefully orchestrated. Similarly, the quadruple helix engagement process should be monitored using a panel management tool to ensure effectiveness.

Emphasizing citizens in our definition is crucial due to their status as the most challenging stakeholder group to engage. While other stakeholder groups such as the public sector, private sector, and academia are equally important, citizens are often less organized and harder to motivate. In FARCLIMATE, particular attention will be paid to inclusion and gender aspects to ensure that citizens represent diverse stakeholder groups.

A two-fold approach can be employed to define **core user personas**, as was tested with FARCLIMATE project partners in February 2024. This was a first workshop held with internal project stakeholders to enhance our understanding of the Living Lab landscape within each regional area across three distinct sectors. Further workshops will follow with the stakeholders representing the case studies. Therefore, while the internal exercise was organised on a theoretical level, the following exercises will become more concrete and will be conducted with personnel from the case studies, working in the local contexts. The definition of the core stakeholders in the case studies should be done within the first four months after their selection. Given that the case studies will be selected in two phases, the delineation of stakeholders will align with their respective start dates for participation.

In the initial stage, a brainstorming exercise is conducted alongside the quadruple helix mapping. Relevant stakeholders are mapped and added to the board (in our case, the workshop was conducted digitally using a Miro board). Following this, the Power vs Interest matrix (Seen in Figure 7) workshop is undertaken. The power-interest matrix is a widely used stakeholder analysis approach, categorized as a top-down or analytical method for classifying stakeholders into four groups based on their relative power and interest, or their interest and influence/relevance over the discussed issue (Ackermann & Eden, 2011). Utilizing the power-interest matrix may unveil fringe stakeholders with limited control and interest in the problem,

who might otherwise be overlooked in the analysis (Reed, M. et al, 2009). In this context, "power" denotes the stakeholder community's ability to impact the discussed matter, while "interests" refer to stakeholders' concerns regarding the topic at hand (Eskafi, M. et al, 2019), encompassing both positive and negative interests.

Figure 7: Power vs Interest Matrix

The power vs interest matrix divides stakeholders into four quadrants:

- In the first quadrant are the **least influential stakeholders**, characterized by low power or interest in the activities. They should be informed through general communication channels like newsletters, as they are unlikely to actively engage in Living Lab activities.
- The second quadrant comprises stakeholders with **significant power but limited interest**. It's essential to **engage** and **consult** with them, addressing their needs to motivate their involvement in the activities.
- Stakeholders in the third quadrant **exhibit high interest but low influence** on the project. They are likely to actively engage in user engagement activities and should be kept informed and invited to participate in engagement events.
- Finally, the fourth quadrant includes **key players**—stakeholders with both high interest and significant influence or power. Engaging with them regularly, consulting them, and involving them in decision-making processes are crucial for the success and sustainability of Living Lab activities.

By implementing dissemination and engagement campaigns, the project can enhance the interest level of stakeholders categorized in the lower quadrants with "low interest" in engagement activities. Through studying their motivations, a better understanding of their needs and incentives for participation can be grasped.

One of the identified project risks involves the potential challenge of motivating key stakeholders with diverse interests in each case study to contribute to the project's common goals. To mitigate this risk, it is recommended to conduct complementary exercises that ensure participants accurately represent the realities of the case. This mapping process will be followed by interviews aimed at uncovering stakeholders' interests and contexts, as well as identifying any new stakeholders not initially recognized. Additionally, recruitment campaigns and engagement activities can be utilized to monitor stakeholders' interest levels and adjust engagement strategies accordingly.

By understanding the mapping exercise, we can strategically "restructure power" to empower relevant stakeholders who may currently have little influence. Overall, the stakeholders with the lower "power" are found to be the citizens. They traditionally lack resources and collective power and are a weakly coordinated group. For example, primary producers such as fishermen and farmers are often the core of communities but may have limited economic and political power. However, their needs, objectives, and knowledge should be integral to the co-creation process. In the quadruple helix collaborations, the public sector, in particular governments, have the strongest formal authority. The private sector is found to have power in their resource advantage, provided by staff and technologies, while research institutes and academia's power lies in critical resources such as human capital and research expertise (Nguyen, 2022). Therefore, the challenge in FARCLIMATE project Living Lab activities is to ensure there is a balance of power and that one stakeholder group doesn't undermine the other. In this way, the Living Lab role is to act as a mediator and an orchestrator and to organise co-creative activities which will empower different stakeholder groups.

In each case study, the core users will constitute a panel, and it's crucial for FARCLIMATE partners to guarantee its balanced representation across various quadruple helix groups. Furthermore, exploration of these groups should delve into factors like gender, age, and ethnicity where appropriate. Building such a panel is intricate and time-consuming, and FARCLIMATE Living Labs need to establish trust with the stakeholders. This entails adhering to ethical practices, tailoring work protocols, and maintaining consistent communication and feedback loops.

4 Living Lab research process for case studies

4.1 Living Lab research, development, and innovation processes

The Living Lab research, development, and innovation processes, as presented in Figure 8, operate seamlessly as a unified whole, each with its own specific role. **The research process** focuses on discovering new knowledge, insights, and understanding about the specific topics a Living Lab is working on. The same principles as in any scientific research should be applied to ensure the reliability and validity of the results. **The development process** aims to systematically explore and develop new solutions or enhance existing ones. This involves hands-on development work where new solution versions are iteratively developed and enhanced based on various co-creation and testing efforts. **The innovation process** focuses on creating and implementing new solutions that will have practical value to contribute to societal, economic, and environmental progress. During the innovation process, user needs and initial ideas are step-by-step transformed into concepts and prototypes to be tested in laboratory, relevant and/or real-life environments, and finally released into the market. In most cases Living Lab process includes transforming solution to lower to higher. Technology Readiness Level (TRL) here is not limited to technology development, instead it refers to any technology, process, or solution which is under development. Thus, in a genuine Living Lab process all the three process elements should exist.

Figure 8: Living Lab research, development, and innovation processes

4.2 Living Lab project journey from customer acquisition to dissemination

Figure 9 presents the Living Lab project journey from customer acquisition to dissemination. The journey can start from a number of different customer touch points for which a Living Lab can offer one of the access options:

- 1) **Excellence-driven** access mode where access is granted on the basis of the peer-reviewed scientific excellence or some other pre-defined criteria such as a result of geomapping,
- 2) **Market-driven** access mode includes a fee and therefore outcome of the study may remain confidential, and
- 3) **Wide access** meaning offering as open access as possible without peer-review or monetary fee requirement.

The visualization of logical relationship between different Living Lab Research and Development (R&D) back-end and auxiliary services (Appendix 1) helps understanding input and output feeds for each service. The Living Lab project journey is divided into 1) customer acquisition, 2) detailed project planning, 3) project implementation and dissemination phases, and 4) innovation ecosystem orchestration which refers to the strategic and operational coordination and management of various elements within a Living Lab innovation ecosystem to foster collaboration, synergy, and overall effectiveness.

Customer acquisition encompasses all activities aimed at securing projects, whether they are public, private, or unfunded. **Detailed project planning** involves defining an implementation plan for newly acquired projects, while **project implementation and dissemination** encompass all the hands-on work to develop new solutions or enhance existing ones. Throughout the project, the journey will be periodically reassessed to ensure comprehensive coverage of FARCLIMATE domain-specific features including forestry, fisheries, and agriculture.

Figure 9: Living Lab project journey from customer acquisition to dissemination

4.3 Living Lab research process

Like any other scientific research process, Living Lab research process includes:

- 1) planning,
- 2) preparation,
- 3) implementation and
- 4) dissemination and valorisation phases.

This sub-chapter focuses on explaining Living Lab research protocol template for detailed project implementation planning. Since FARCLIMATE consist of multiple case studies, a **cross-case study approach** is adopted (Yin, R. K., 2009). Case study leaders are responsible for case study level data collect and within-case analysis. ENOLL in collaboration with Laurea and CERTH, will oversee the collation of findings from all case studies, enabling a comprehensive and systematic view of the collective data. Cross Case Analysis is created by following similar analysis approach as in the within-case analysis. Therefore, throughout the project it is important that data form case studies are collected using similar frameworks. For that, 1) a common method and tools, 2) devices and technologies and 3) validated questionnaires and other instruments are collected to generate to identify common data collection approaches between the cases.

A research protocol template that will be used is grounded on Template For Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) (Hoffmann, T.C. et al, 2014) and modified for Living Lab purposes. The template will include:

- 1) study title,
- 2) short explanation of study rationale / background and significance,
- 3) primary and secondary objectives,
- 4) expected outcomes and impact,
- 5) inclusion and exclusion criteria for primary and secondary users,
- 6) sample size and
- 7) recruitment strategy.

Each phase of the Living Lab Technology Readiness Level (details provided in the next section) includes an explanation of its components. These are:

- 1) What (procedures, activities, and methods),
- 2) What (materials, technologies, and devices),
- 3) Where (Research environment),
- 4) How (modes of delivery),
- 5) When and how much (Scheduling, date, and duration),
- 6) Who provides (Research team and their roles) and
- 7) Ethical considerations and issues. Research protocol template is a living document, which will be updated during the process.

As a part cross-case study process, the common

- 1) methods and tools,
- 2) devices and technologies, and
- 3) validated questionnaires and instruments useful for sustainability studies in context of forestry, fisheries and agriculture will be collected.

This kind of data will help to gain holistic understanding what kind of data project can generate and to make sure the interoperability between the case studies.

4.4 Living Lab Technology Readiness Level (LLTRL)

The key aim during the FARCLIMATE is to co-create and validate new nature-based solutions that are environmentally friendly and economically affordable as well as to develop an inspiring and empowering communication approach, in order to take the first steps to create a European climate-resilience communities' network.

Figure 10 presents a common Living Lab activity across the different TRL level. The aim of the table is to highlight what kind of exploratory and confirmatory research aims are done during each phase and to describe the solution maturity level. This framework will be used for tracking the evolution of the developed solutions.

Figure 7 is the result of merging the Technology readiness levels (TRL) defined by Horizon Europe (Horizon 2020, 2014) and the common Living Lab activities during the different (TRL).

Innovation process phase name and description	R&D envir.	Solution name	Functionality / Interactivity	Solution maturity	Exploratory research aim	Confirmatory research aim	
TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation: A need is a measurable gap between two conditions: what currently is and what should be, whereas ideation is a process of creating and prioritizing new ideas. The key objectives are to identify market demand, potential users, user needs, latent needs, (hidden) problems, competitive landscape and challenge these from different stakeholders perspective. Often a state of the art of the current scientific literature is also covered to define what is already known in prior research.	Laboratory (observations in operational)	Idea	None	A group of needs, problems, opportunities and/or ideas identified. Not been proven feasible.	Investigate a problem or topic to generate new ideas and hypotheses.	Prioritize needs and ideas.	
TRL 2: Concept co-creation: Concept is high-level, abstract representation of an idea describing the overall vision and direction of the developed solution. Co-creation refers to collaboration in which various key stakeholders are actively contributing in solution development. Defines and prioritizes solution key characteristics and makes value proposition hypothesis by exploring and co-creating various options with relevant key stakeholders. Defines user requirements, creates user stories and personas.	Laboratory	Visual / Textual prototype	None, or very limited	High-level speculative and static concept transforming to concept prototype without or very limited functionality. Focuses on explaining and describing overall design concept and user interactions. Based on sketches, diagrams, drawings, compositions, mockups, wireframes, digital models, storyboards, paper interface and/or descriptive text. Non interactive to very limited interactivity.	Investigate a topic in more detailed to co-create and formulate concept and value hypotheses in iterative or parallel manner.	Prioritize options to determine the most appropriate way to proceed with further development.	
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC): By collect feedback and improvement suggestions for the different concept variations, POC verifies if a high level concept is accepted by potential users and other relevant stakeholders. Initial feasibility study shows whether the concept can be developed. Evaluate technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept.	Laboratory	Alpha prototype	Very limited	User experience / working prototypes transforming from low to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. First working models to identify and resolve usability, design and technical issues. Can have substantial flaws or missing functions.	Explore different human, technical, economic, and environmental aspect to verify what is the best approach to develop the solution.	Test value hypothesis and confirm or reject them. Focus on user acceptance and feasibility.	
TRL 4: Prototyping in lab: Co-create quickly multiple design variations, features and functionalities by following rapid prototyping approach. Lab test prototype functionality, usability, and user acceptance in iterative co-creation-test cycle. Identify and address any immediate design flaws, usability problems or issues relating user acceptance before proceeding to next phase.	Laboratory		Limited		Moderate	Co-create rapid functional prototype versions. Focus on the basic functionalities.	Verify usability, and technical feasibility to find out the most promising options having highest cost/profit ratio and user acceptance.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment: Transform from user experience / working prototypes to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected in relevant environment and meets the predictions.	Relevant						
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment: Verify that high-fidelity prototype which closely resemble the final solution adequately addresses all critical features in relevant environment. Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.	Relevant	Beta prototype	High or near full	High-fidelity prototype with near fully functionality that closely resemble the final solution and adequately addresses all critical features. Technical feasibility fully demonstrated.	Continue to iteratively refine the prototype based on the collected feedback and co-creation inputs.	Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.	
TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment: Validate that near final solution (or final solution) is functioning at system level in operational environment. Start at scale and by using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment.	Operational		Near full or full			Production prototype near final solution (or final solution) functioning at system level	By using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment. Start in small scale and increase the scale gradually to full scale.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment: Validate final solution in operational environment. Focus on similar issues as in TRL 7 but in more large scale and longer duration.	Operational	Pilot prototype	Full	Final complete solution at system level.	Refine and commit to final solution.		
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance: Monitoring the safety, quality and performance after solution has been released on the market. Focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions. Evaluate long term social and business impact. Help businesses make informed decisions that can lead to increased sales, growth and new opportunities.	Operational	Final solution	Full	Final complete solution at system level ready for sale.	Refinement via versioning strategy.	Monitor and evaluate safety, effectiveness, performance and quality over longer period of time.	

Figure 10 Common Living Lab activities during the different TRL level

5 Developing Living Labs

5.1 Living Lab Mapping Canvas

The process of selecting, engaging, and developing governance and empowerment plans for each community will involve various steps as defined in T2.1. These steps will be fine-tuned and adapted to suit the socio-cultural context of each community or city where the project will occur. The selection process will adhere to the methodology and requirements established by the consortium, with assistance from the Living Lab mapping canvas.

The Living Lab Mapping Canvas, developed by ENOLL, serves as a tool to outline the key components of Living Labs, aiding in understanding their level of maturity. Initially crafted in 2019 as part of the EU-funded URBANOME project⁴ (GA ID 945391), this canvas has since been customized for various areas of work. The canvas, presented in Figure 11 has been specifically tailored to FARCLIMATE project and the Case Studies. This chapter introduces the Mapping Canvas, followed by suggested workshops to populate its sections. The Canvas is also aligned with the Living Lab three-layer model classification approach demonstrated in Figure 4. As the FARCLIMATE project aims to develop certifiable Living Labs, the Canvas has been modified to target the Macro level development. In particular, yellow quadrants are essential for establishing a Living Lab at a Macro level, and orange quadrants applicable across all levels: Macro, Meso, and Micro.

The empowerment plan will serve as a roadmap for implementation within the project's case study and for scaling up the Living Lab. It will also be utilized for monitoring and fine-tuning progress.

⁴ <https://www.urbanome.eu/>

Living Lab Mapping Canvas

Interactive canvas for Living Labs (case studies) to help them develop a sustainable Living Lab and engage the quadruple helix

Color index

- Macro level of the living lab
- Meso level of the living lab
- Micro level of the living lab
- All levels of the living lab

Name:

Name of the Living Lab:

Date:

<p>People & Internal Roles What are our names, emails and the roles we have in the team?</p> <p>Living Lab Manager</p> <p>Project Manager</p> <p>Pilot manager</p> <p>Panel Manager</p> <p>Human interaction specialist</p> <p>Communicator</p>	<p>Vision & Scope What is the vision and scope of the LL? Scope = the extent of the area or subject matter that something deals with or to which it is relevant. Vision = what do you aim to achieve in the long-run</p>	<p>Stakeholders & External Roles For Whom What quadruple helix stakeholders are you already in touch with? Please list top 5</p>	<p>Overview of all Stakeholders Map all relevant stakeholder onto a panel square, based on the quadruple helix model</p>
<p>Host organisation Who is your host organisation (e.g. public body - municipality, private body, research institute)</p>		<p>The Living Lab Context Where the solutions will be tested /implemented?</p>	
<p>Strategy</p>		<p>SWOT</p>	<p>LL Communication Strategy & Channels The communication strategy will incorporate sections on communication at a local level. What communications channels do you already have (e.g. communication strategy, social media, website, newsletter, etc.) and are you planning on establishing any new communications channels?</p>
<p>Governance The governance and management structure reflects on the way that an LL in the strategic or operational level is managed and organised.</p>		<p>Value for the stakeholders</p>	<p>Monitoring & evaluation How will you measure the succes of activities, projects and the LL over all?</p>
<p>Resources & sustainability Material (incl. finances) & human resources to support long-term commitment? In other words, what does the business model of your living lab looks like? Who are the financiers? In addition, what do they bring and who will pay you and for what? What does the LL maintenance plan look like? Collaboration strategies & business plan for the future</p>			

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 Please request authorization to use part or the entire canvas
 Unauthorized use can lead to legal implications
 info@enoll.org

Figure 11: Living Lab Mapping Canvas

The mapping activity begins in the centre of the canvas by defining the **purpose** of the Living Lab and articulating "**why**" are we developing the Living Lab or using the Living Lab methodology in the first place.

Next, the **vision and scope** of the Living Lab are identified. Scope refers to the "extent of the area or subject matter that something deals with or to which it is relevant" while the vision outlines long-term objectives to be achieved. In the case of FARCLIMATE, these would normally be aligned with the vision and scope of the project. For instance, when it comes to scope, the Living Lab would outline in which sector it is working and explain their particular activity in as many details as possible.

In the quadrant representing the **host organization**, details such as the name and type of the hosting organization (e.g., municipality, research institute, university, private company, etc.) are provided. The host organisation will have a direct influence on the governance model of the Living Lab and the internal intricacies.

The "**stakeholders and external roles**" quadrant identifies the top five stakeholders with whom the Living Lab maintains contact, derived from the Power vs Interest Matrix exercise shown in Figure 7.

In the "**overview of stakeholders**" quadrant, an overview of the quadruple helix stakeholders with whom the Living Lab is engaged or has identified for its operations is presented. Additional information on the quadruple helix and the importance of involving these stakeholders in the co-creation process is provided in Chapter 2 of the deliverable.

Brainstorming and stakeholder mapping exercise is crucial to ensure that the Living Labs have considered all potential actors who may have an interest in or be affected by the project. This approach is essential for fostering inclusivity and ensuring that the perspectives of all relevant parties are considered. The exercises should be done in combination with the **Power vs Interest Matrix** exercise. The latter is completed to determine the key stakeholders that have the highest influence in the project and map all other stakeholders based on their level of interest and influence on the Living Lab activities. This exercise has been presented in Chapter 2 and is shown in Figure 7.

The **communication** strategy and channels are defined under the stakeholders, primarily overseen by the communicator role within the Living Lab. A well-defined communication strategy is crucial for effective engagement.

Beneath the communication section, **monitoring and evaluation** of activities are addressed. This involves the implementation of a panel management system to monitor the engagement and plan activities of external stakeholders.

The **internal roles** of the Living Lab should be outlined on the left-hand side of the canvas. This quadrant includes all staff members involved in the Living Lab activities, including the Living Lab Manager, Project Manager, Pilot Manager, Panel Manager, Human Interaction Specialist, and the Communicator. The roles are presented in Table 1. It is important to note, that while these roles align with the theoretical research on Living Labs (ENoLL, 2019) they may not look like this in practice. It is possible for one individual to fulfil multiple roles.

Table 1: Internal roles in a Living Lab

Role Name	Role Description
Living Lab Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most apparent internal role. • Initiator and keeper of the Living Lab strategy. • Manages Living Lab's everyday activities. • Ensures that a Living Lab is maintained effectively and sustainably.
Project Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for the management of a particular Living Lab project.
Pilot Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up, run, and scale up the technologies during the pilot project(s). • Facilitates the implementation and test of the innovation.
Panel Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for recruiting and interacting with a panel of stakeholders involved in testing and evaluation activities. • Decides which users need to be involved in the process and manages communication with them.
Human Interaction Specialist	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performs user-centred interactions. • Analyses the results from different human interaction methods. • Responsible for testing solutions before their implementation in the real-life context. • Referred to as the researcher in certain papers.
Communicator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creates and implements different communication strategies.

Within the **strategy quadrant**, the Living Labs will outline the outcomes of the 5 Bold Steps exercise, a collaborative process aimed at crafting both the vision and the actionable steps required to realize that vision. This exercise serves as a platform for co-designing the strategic direction of the Living Lab, ensuring alignment with overarching goals and objectives.

The 5 bold steps exercise, developed by David Sibbet, of the Grove International, can be used to align the Living Lab team in establishing the vision, scope and strategy and ideate on 5 concrete steps that will be taken to achieve it. The canvas depicted in Figure 12 serves as a tool for envisioning Living Lab goals. Through this canvas, the internal team can identify factors that reinforce the Living Lab vision, as well as those that pose challenges and present opportunities. It is also an important exercise to the subsequent Business Model Canvas.

Figure 12: 5 Bold Steps canvas

Within the **SWOT** quadrant, the Living Labs will conduct an analysis of the Living Lab's internal and external factors, including its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This assessment is derived from the SWOT analysis exercise conducted within the Living Lab.

The SWOT analysis is a simple tool, where the Living Lab team brainstorms on their strengths and weaknesses pertaining to internal factors, such as resources, capabilities, and operational aspects. On the other hand, opportunities and threats relate to external factors, such as market dynamics, regulatory changes, and competitive landscape. By systematically evaluating these factors, the Living Lab gains valuable insights into its current position and strategic considerations for future development. For a Living Lab to attain sustainability, it must comprehend its own strengths, values, and weaknesses (Bodi, Z., de Los Rios White, M., Enriquez, L., 2020). While Living Labs must address these aspects, they should also prioritize the development of a stable business models.

Next, the **governance** model of the organisation should be defined to understand the internal intricacies and how the decision-making process is conducted within the Living Labs. This naturally leads to the next quadrant focused on the **value** for stakeholders, which is intricately intertwined with the established governance model.

The governance model exercise assists in outlining and defining the governance structure of the Living Lab and its internal functions. Firstly, the Living Lab should map out the people and internal roles, followed by defining their governance model. This involves determining how the Living Lab will be managed both strategically and operationally. The governance model differs across Living Labs and is tailored to each context and depends on their host organization. In FARCLIMATE, our role will be to aid Living Labs in defining their governance model, which is a crucial step preceding the definition of Business Models.

Through qualitative research conducted on Urban Living Lab governance models, (Voorwinden, A. et al, 2023) discovered a spectrum of formalization existing within Living Lab configurations, spanning from informal to highly formalized structures. The level of formalization is shaped by financial, legal, and organizational elements that evolve over time and are associated with inherent trade-offs, even if these trade-offs are not explicitly acknowledged by stakeholders. Their study underscores the potential benefits for Urban Living Labs in clearly delineating the legal frameworks that influence their structure, operations, and future trajectory.

In the bottom quadrant, the **business model** of the Living Lab is defined, including the information on what kind of resources are needed. This includes a comprehensive breakdown of the necessary resources essential for the smooth functioning of the Living Lab, clarifying the financial, human, and infrastructural requirements essential for its operations. The **business model canvas** can be used for this exercise.

A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). Business Model Canvas (BMC), seen in Figure 13 consisting the following nine different elements is a common approach to describe business model: (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. List of Living Lab business model elements as defined by Horizon funded VITALISE-project and presented in Appendix 2 is utilized for FARCLIMATE purposes and updated based domain specific attributes. The business model elements will help updating the Mapping Canvas and verify that all the relevant aspects of business model will be covered.

KEY PARTNERS The network of suppliers and partners that make the Business Model (BM) work	KEY ACTIVITIES The most important things an organization must do to make its BM work	VALUE PROPOSITIONS The bundle of products and services that create value for a specific <i>Customer segments</i>	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS Types of relationships an organization establishes with specific <i>Customer segments</i>	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS Different groups of people or organizations an organization aims to reach and serve
	KEY RESOURCES The most important assets required to make a BM work		CHANNELS How organization communicates and reaches its <i>Customer segments</i>	
COST STRUCTURE All costs incurred to operate a Business Model (BM)			REVENUE STREAMS Revenues an organization generates from each <i>Customer segment</i>	

Figure 13: Business Model Canvas by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010)

Figure 9 illustrates the Business Model Canvas, comprising the following segments:

- **Key Resources:** Identifying crucial physical, financial, intellectual, or human assets.
- **Key activities:** Identifying the most important activities the Living Lab will do to make its Business Model work.
- **Key partners:** Strategically selecting and optimizing partners and networks to access resources and capabilities lacking within the company.
- **Value Proposition:** Describing the benefits customers can anticipate from the bundle of services and products offered by the company.
- **Customer Segments:** Defining distinct groups of people or organizations sharing common attributes and targeted by the company to receive a range of services and products.
- **Channels:** Identifying various communication, distribution, and sales channels utilized by the company to reach and deliver its products and services to customers.
- **Customer Relationships:** Outlining the ongoing management process to foster relationships and interactions with both current and potential customers.
- **Cost Structure:** Highlighting the significant financial implications incurred to execute key activities and operate the business model.
- **Revenue Streams:** Defining the various methods through which the company captures value and generates income from different customer segments by meeting their expectations.

Figure 14, shows an example of the Business Model attributes from (ProVaHealth, 2020) Here the values are demonstrated with a heat map. The individual attributes are color-coded, with green representing high relevance and red indicating low relevance. The variables in the heat map are arranged in colour based on their level of mean value. The responses with highest mean value are in dark green, while responses with the lowest mean value are in dark red.

BM ELEMENTS	LIVING LAB BUSINESS MODEL ATTRIBUTES – RELATIVE IMPORTANCE 2021									
KEY PARTNERS	Research org. [6.87]	Regional public org. [6.13]	Municipals and cities [6.00]	Networks and Clusters [6.67]	State level org. [4.33]	Digital service providers [5.60]	NGOs, and third sector org. [4.27]			
	Education org. [6.73]	Secondary care org. [5.73]	Device manufacturers [7.00]	Tertiary care org. [4.80]	Primary care org. [5.07]	Preventive health / wellbeing service providers [4.40]				
KEY ACTIVITIES	Project mgmt. [6.20]	Testing and co-creation [7.80]	Funding support services [5.73]	Marketing and sales [4.87]	End-user services [2.13]	Support services to state authorities [3.00]				
	Education and training [6.60]	Ecosystem orchestration [6.33]	Support services to regional authorities [3.93]	Support services to local authorities [3.73]	Funding [2.27]					
KEY RESOURCES	Personnel [6.87]	Infra and technologies [6.47]	Partner(s) [5.40]	External networks [5.40]	User and patients panel [5.47]	Students [4.93]	Data and publication databases [5.67]	External experts [4.40]	IPR-portfolio [3.00]	
VALUE PROPOSITIONS	R&D Services [6.60]	With real end-user [6.40]	Customized services [4.87]	Ecosystem and project mgmt. [5.07]	Funding support [4.60]	Method development [4.00]	Funding [3.13]			
	Unique infrastructure [6.60]	Various positive arguments [6.47]	Multi-disciplinary [5.80]	Value and impact evaluation [5.07]	Education and training [4.73]	Marketing Support [3.33]				
CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS	Long-term relations [7.53]	Project based [6.73]	Direct personal contacts [6.47]	Networking [6.33]	Events [4.93]	Internal [4.47]	Co-Creation with various stakeholders [6.07]	Steering [3.67]	Advisory [3.47]	
CHANNELS	Co-operation projects [7.07]	Regional channel [4.93]	Educational channels [4.47]	Events arranged by LL [5.40]	Professional publications [5.20]	Scientific publications [3.47]	Online, mobile and social media [4.73]	Paid media and marketing [2.40]		
	Direct channels [6.33]	Event participation [5.27]	Networks and cluster [5.93]	Owners or key partners channels [4.13]	Municipal and city channels [4.40]	Lobbying and policy channels [4.80]	State level channel [3.13]			
CUSTOMER SEGMENTS	Education org. [5.20]	Device manufacturers [5.27]	Research org. [4.53]	Municipals and cities [4.67]	State level org. [3.33]	Tertiary care org. [3.80]	NGOs, and third sector org. [2.80]			
	Regional public Org. [4.93]	Digital service providers [6.27]	Secondary care org. [4.53]	Primary care org. [4.08]	Networks and clusters [5.00]	Preventive health/wellbeing service providers [4.47]				
COST STRUCTURE	Personnel [8.07]	Infrastructure and facilities cost [5.53]	Internal R&D development [4.80]	Travelling costs [3.20]	Consulting fees for external experts [3.07]	IPR-protection [2.60]	End-User fees and other variable costs [3.40]	Outsourced services [2.60]	Marketing and sales [3.47]	
REVENUE STREAMS	Project grants [6.33]	Fixed or permanent funding [6.40]	R&D project and consulting service sales [3.33]	Education and training services [2.40]	Device and infrastructure rental [2.27]	Donations [2.27]	Royalties [1.73]	Event and site visit fees [1.60]	Equipment and device retail [0.53]	

Figure 14: Living Lab Business Model Attributes (Santonen, T et al, 2020)

5.2 Training in Case Studies

To ensure that the key components of Living Labs are implemented and developed, the FARCLIMATE Living Lab training process will be structured with the help of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas. A specific training methodology will be suggested for each topic on the Mapping Canvas, designed to assist Living Labs in defining their key components.

A Living Lab Crash Course conducted within WP4 *Transversal solutions: training and empowerment for communities* will facilitate the FARCLIMATE core teams in establishing a unified understanding and vision of Living Labs. Online introductory sessions were already conducted within the consortium to introduce Living Labs, with additional introductory sessions planned for stakeholders from the case studies. A program outline will be prepared every 6 months and implemented through monthly activities. Following selection, each community will undergo a series of online group trainings to acquaint themselves with Living Lab principles and basic methods. Each Living Lab will designate a profile and reference person responsible for collecting challenges and proposed solutions co-designed with community members.

Training modules will be defined by Month 12, as reported in D4.1 Training modules/curriculum and methodology, with the online training platform developed by Month 20. Testing of training occurs between Months 13-24, and case studies are trained between Months 20-28 to 45, depending on the target audience. Additionally, the conceptual and methodological basis for the Living Labs will be finalized by Month 15, as outlined in Milestone 5.

6 Living Lab Evaluation Framework

Continuous evaluation of the Living Labs will occur in 6-month rotation cycles. Each evaluation will refine planned case activities, as well as the overall Living Lab strategy and business model based on insights gathered. At the project's conclusion, the Deliverable D2.4 *Compilation of Living Labs Factsheets* will compile strategic plans of the Living Lab. To facilitate the evaluation process, the framework presented in this chapter is proposed, which has been developed by ENoLL as part of the alignment efforts within the VITALISE H2020 project. This framework is designed to assess the maturity levels of existing Living Labs or those aspiring to attain Living Lab status. The Living Lab Evaluation Framework functions as a standardized instrument for assessing and gaining insights into Living Labs. Its findings yield a set of recommendations for areas requiring enhancement, thereby optimizing Living Lab operations to deliver improved services, impact, and sustainability. The framework complements the quadrant on Monitoring and Evaluation of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas.

The framework encompasses a range of evaluation criteria across Macro, Meso, and Micro levels of Living Labs (Schuurman, 2015), as detailed in Chapter 2. Moreover, it integrates a series of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specifically formulated for Living Labs. Through the utilization of these KPIs, the Living Labs can increase their capacity to consistently measure their performance, thereby enhancing their efficiency, transparency, and influence in fostering innovation and sustainable development.

The FARCLIMATE project stands to gain from the Living Lab Evaluation Framework, particularly by leveraging the KPIs to support and direct the self-assessment of aspiring Living Lab members within the project. The Living Labs will be assessed on these KPIs with the aim of becoming certified Living Labs by the end of the project duration.

The Evaluation framework developed by Vervoort et al. (2022) is divided into 5 different chapters:

- Strategy
- Operations
- Openness
- Users & Reality
- Impact & value
- Stability & harmonization

These are further divided into different specific criterions, for which specific KPIs are defined. Table 2: KPIs for Living Labs (ENoLL, 2023) presents an overview of the KPIs which form the evaluation framework.

Table 2: KPIs for Living Labs (ENoLL, 2023)

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Strategy	Governance	1. % of (active) involvement of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the development of the vision & mission of the Living Lab (e.g., all Q4 represented is 100%)
		2. % of participation of a balanced and diverse group of stakeholders in the governance of the Living Lab (strategic & operational roles and decision-making processes)
		3. Presence of partner agreements/arrangements for co-innovation
		4. Completeness of a strategic roadmap for the Living Lab (SMART goals, responsibilities, and decision-making processes)
	Business Model	5. Completeness of the described business model approach (value propositions, problems & solutions, activities & resources, key stakeholders, customers, users, costs & revenues, metrics & impacts)
		6. Number of (different) services offered by the Living Lab (e.g., stakeholder engagement) covering (all) different phases of the innovation cycle
	Culture & Collaboration	7. Presence of internal & external business & client relation management process/strategy (including contracts)
		8. Frequency of internal communication & results sharing to keep partners informed & aligned
		9. Number of regional, national & international collaborations beyond the scope of an individual Living Lab project
Operations	Human Resources	10. % of Implementation of needed internal roles and responsibilities within the operational Living Lab team in a flexible way (are all roles sufficiently attributed depending on the size of the operational Living Lab team)
	Operations	11. Time spent within successfully completed projects and/or activities related to the Living Lab (how many weeks/months/years of experience does the Living Lab has in running projects and/or activities)
		12. Completeness & frequency of internal self-monitoring processes (how often is the Living Lab monitoring essential parts of their organization: strategic, financial, equipment & infrastructure, policy, project outcomes)
	Equipment & infrastructure	13. % accessibility in time to facilities (e.g., offices, co-creation spaces, testing facilities...)
		14. % accessibility in time to hard- & software (e.g., co-creation materials, computers, wearables, interaction software, polling/survey software...)
	Openness	Innovation partnerships, projects & processes
16. % of implementation of needed processes to safeguard an ethical approach (e.g., regulatory requirements, data protection needed, etc.)		
Ownership of results		17. % of implementation of needed rules & regulations regarding the use, sharing & licensing of data and IP of collaborative outcomes
		18. % of implementation of user agreements (data, IPR, rights, liabilities)

Chapter	Criterion	KPI
Users & reality	User centricity	19. % of diversity of stakeholders involved as end-users in Living Lab projects and/or activities
		20. Degree of influence end-users exerts on the different phases of the innovation cycle (from informing to empowerment)
	Lifecycle & real-life	21. Degree of involvement of end-users in the different phases of the innovation cycle e.g., problem space, solution space, implementation space...)
		22. Degree of use of real-life contexts of users in the different phases of the innovation cycle
	Tools & methods	23. Degree of appropriateness of tools & methods used for the different phases of the innovation cycle
		24. Frequency of external communication & results sharing to keep end-users and external stakeholders informed and engaged
Impact & value	Co-created values	25. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders (from the whole value chain) concerning their involvement/influence on the innovation cycle
		26. Number of relevant (open) educational resources (including datasets, trainings) shared/provided for relevant stakeholders
		27. % Satisfaction of users/stakeholders concerning knowledge sharing & capacity building (learning materials & infrastructures)
	Impacts	28. Completeness & frequency of impact assessments (how often is the Living Lab monitoring different types of impacts they are generating: societal, environmental, economic, regulatory, academic)
Stability & harmonization	Stability	29. % Increase in number of relationships (with a reliable partner network and customers)
		30. Level of financial sustainability based on a balanced & diversified set of fundings (structural vs. project-based) & revenue streams
		31. Number of Living Lab value propositions, flexible to adapt to new circumstances
	Harmonization & scale-up	32. % Increase in number of partners committed to scale up products/solutions/services developed by the Living Lab
		33. Number of products/solutions/services (able to be) scaled-up
		34. Number of participation in (cross-border/cross-sectoral) initiatives/projects based on harmonized Living Lab infrastructures, standards, skills, methods, tools processes or services

Strategy

The first chapter on Living Lab strategy delves into the macro-level dynamics of a Living Lab, emphasizing multi-stakeholder participation and the orchestrating role of the Living Lab. It evaluates the Living Lab against three key criteria (Vervoort, K. et al, 2023):

- **Governance:** This includes a well-defined vision and mission, rooted in the identified needs of the quadruple helix, with regular and flexible reviews. It also involves the active engagement of all quadruple helix actors at a strategic level within a flexible partner network. Additionally, it includes a clearly defined team structure and responsibilities within the Living Lab management team, along with a clear description of expected impacts.
- **Business Model:** This aspect focuses on sustainable finances and a well-defined service portfolio catering to various innovation and collaboration processes.
- **Culture:** This involves demonstrating connections and interest in external innovation ecosystems, fostering smart and adaptive cooperation within the Living Lab to build trust, and ensuring quality internal communication processes to enhance trust-building efforts across macro, meso, and micro levels.

Operations

The operational aspects of a Living Lab, address equipment, infrastructure, and human resources management across all levels of operations. Here three key evaluation criteria are outlined:

- **Operations:** Demonstrating experience in conducting Living Lab projects and activities, including case examples (meso-micro), implementing monitoring processes for operational aspects such as research and project management (macro-meso), monitoring the impact of Living Lab activities, projects, and overall strategy (macro-meso-micro), establishing partner agreements (macro-meso), and defining branding and positioning (macro-meso).
- **Human Resources:** Ensuring availability and allocation of qualified staff across different roles and responsibilities (macro) and ensuring role flexibility based on evolving needs (macro-meso).
- **Equipment & Infrastructure:** Ensuring access to necessary equipment and infrastructure (e.g., software, hardware, spaces), and ensuring timely availability of required resources (this can be applied to all three levels: macro-meso-micro).

Openness

The chapter on "Openness" examines the transparency and collaborative nature of the Living Lab across macro, meso, and micro levels, focusing on processes, partnerships, feedback mechanisms, and intellectual property (IP) protection. Two evaluation criteria are outlined:

- **Innovation Processes & Partnerships:** Evaluating the presence of legal agreements addressing Living Lab responsibilities (macro-meso), transparency of data agreements with partners, stakeholders, and users (macro-meso), overall transparency level (macro), and openness to new partnerships and investors (macro).

- **Ownership of Results:** Assessing feedback protection measures (meso-micro), delineation between shared and formal ownership (macro-meso), and effectiveness of IP processes supporting openness and capability (meso-micro).

Users & Reality

This chapter explores collaboration methods and levels of engagement in real-world scenarios, focusing on the implementation of iterative Living Lab processes and the effectiveness of tools and methods used. Within this chapter, three evaluation criteria are outlined:

- **Quality of Iterative Living Lab Processes:** Assessing the adoption of iterative processes based on lifecycle or integrative approaches (meso) and user involvement in real-life settings (meso-micro).
- **User-Centricity of Engagement Approach:** Evaluating the description and intensity of user participation and impact on innovation processes (macro-meso), representativeness and permanence of user panels (macro-meso), and level of user involvement in Living Lab activities (micro).
- **Quality of Participatory Tools & Methods:** Examining engagement strategies to meet evolving user needs (macro-meso), variety and innovation of tools and methods used (meso-micro), and effectiveness of communication processes to attract new partners, stakeholders, and users (macro-meso).

Impact & Value creation

The chapter on "Impact & Value Creation" evaluates the co-created values and various impact aspects of the Living Lab across all levels. Two evaluation criteria are outlined:

- **Co-created Values:** Assessing user and stakeholder satisfaction, knowledge exchange, academic validation, network knowledge sharing, capacity building, technology readiness level, value chain coverage, and value capture strategies.
- **Impact of the Living Lab:** Examining internal impact on learning, societal impact (e.g., behavioural change, inclusion), economic impact (e.g., patents, market disruption), environmental impact (e.g., pollution reduction), and regulatory impact (e.g., public policies).

Stability & harmonisation

"Stability & Harmonization," chapter delves into the financial stability and strategic alignment of the Living Lab at a macro-level. It examines various aspects such as business model, service offerings, and strategy plans, aiming to enhance sustainability through harmonization with other entities. Two evaluation criteria are defined:

- **Stability of the Living Lab:** Assessing funding achievement, new partnerships, network collaboration, SWOT analysis, and future business plans.
- **Harmonization & Scaling-Up:** Evaluating adoption of standardized procedures, project management processes, tools, methods & technologies, replicability of services, quality of collaboration, and knowledge sharing with other entities.

7 Conclusion

The FARCLIMATE project aims to establish 20 Living Labs in the case studies, with 9 of them to be certified by ENoLL labelling and certification committee. Achieving this goal is ambitious, considering the complexity of certifying Living Labs, which requires not only demonstrating true application of the Living Lab methodology but also sustainability of operations. Hence, this deliverable, along with upcoming trainings developed by FARCLIMATE project partners, will assist case studies in developing Living Labs at a Macro level, incorporating fully formed operations, governance, and sustainability models. This support will be provided throughout the project's 48-month timeline. This deliverable outlines a trajectory for Living Lab development, offering guidance for the FARCLIMATE case studies. Building a Living Lab on a regional or community level involves creating a collaborative environment where diverse stakeholders, including citizens, businesses, researchers, and local authorities, collaborate to co-create and test innovative solutions aimed at tackling local challenges.

The process of developing and operating a Living Lab can be summarised in four steps that follow the Open Innovation Community process as illustrated in Figure 15, integrating the fundamental principles of the Living Lab approach.

Figure 15 Open innovation communities' approach in Living Labs context

Strengthening Local Capacity

This first step helps each Living Lab to create fertile ground for adopting innovation by consuming the capacities of the local ecosystem and by using common knowledge & understanding of the problems to be solved. One of the first activities to be performed is the identification of local challenges. This may involve gathering input from stakeholders through surveys, interviews, workshops, and community meetings and a thorough assessment of the region or community to identify strengths and weaknesses as well as key challenges and opportunities. The identification of the local challenges is a critical step for clearly defining the objectives and scope of the Living Lab. The objectives of a Living Lab can be related to a specific sector (e.g. agriculture, fisheries, forestry) or to different focus areas/sectors such as climate neutrality or sustainability. This step is incorporated in the Mapping Canvas within the sections concerning the objectives, scope, and strategy.

Gearing Ecosystem Capacity

Building a diverse network of stakeholders from the quadruple helix who are willing to participate in the Living Lab and keeping them actively engaged pursuing a co-creation and co-design strategy of solutions is an activity of high importance. The collaboration with the stakeholders and the citizens throughout the whole process of designing, developing, and testing new solutions, ensures high levels of solutions' acceptance and Living Labs continuity and reliability, which are among the basic priorities of our Living Lab. The strong liaison of the Living Lab with public and private stakeholders encouraging cross-sector collaboration and creativity, the continuous focus on innovation for problem solving and the support in decision making are among the main characteristics that a Living Lab must adopt. Stakeholders' relationships, needs and expectations should also be mapped in this stage along with the identification of the ways they can contribute to the achievement of Living Lab goals. The "veto" players whose decision has more impact in the achievement, or the non-achievement of a Living Labs' goal need also to be identified. This step is integrated into the Stakeholders quadrant of the mapping canvas and incorporated into the governance exercise. The "veto" players can also be identified through the Power Vs Interest Matrix.

The development of a collaborative governance structure that outlines roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes enhances effective coordination and co-creation among diverse stakeholders. It also facilitates the value proposition creation for stakeholder.

Accelerating innovation

At this stage the solutions are developing within the Living Lab and can be tested in real-world settings. This may involve conducting pilot projects, demonstrations, experiments, or field trials to assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness. Data and feedback from stakeholders are collected throughout the prototyping and testing phases using qualitative and quantitative methods to evaluate the impact of the solutions on addressing the identified challenges and achieving the desired outcomes. The Living Lab research process for case studied aids the FARCLIMATE Living Labs in their data collection.

The development of an action plan that defines the required actions and the time plan of the Living Lab implementation, the identification of the resources (financial and human) to support long-term sustainability and of the factors that are related to the political, economic, social, technological, and environmental viability of the Living Lab are required for alleviating the barriers at this stage. This phase is conducted using the governance and business model exercises outlined in the Mapping Canvas.

Scaling-up innovation

Monitoring and evaluation of the success of solutions, projects and the Living Lab is indispensable activity of this stage. By continuously iterating and refining the solutions based on the feedback received from stakeholders and the results of testing and embracing a culture of experimentation, learning, and adaptation contribute to the improvement of the effectiveness of the solutions over time. For this step the list of KPIs has been presented, which is also incorporated into Monitoring & Evaluation quadrants of the Mapping Canvas.

An effective communication strategy ensures the sharing of knowledge including best practices, lessons learned and success stories from the Living Lab with other communities,

organizations, and stakeholders. This knowledge exchange and collaboration can be integrated in strategies that aim to sustain the momentum of the Living Lab initiative beyond the initial phases and explore opportunities at a broader level enabling the scaling up, transferability and replicability of successful solutions to other regions or communities.

By following the recommendations provided in this deliverable, User-driven Living Labs can be effectively established on a regional or community level to drive innovation, collaboration, and sustainable development. By utilizing the Living Lab Mapping Canvas and complementary exercises, alongside the Living Lab evaluation framework and its corresponding KPIs as guiding tools, Living Labs can attain macro level maturity and achieve certification status by the end of the FARCLIMATE project.

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Appendix 1: List of Living Lab services

SERVICE NAME	Service type			Process phase		
	R&D	Back-office	Auxiliary	Customer acquisition	Detailed project planning	Project implementation
Access to data	1			1		
Capacity building	1			1		
Clinical trials	1					1
Co-creation sessions	1					1
Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	1					1
Concept and proof-of-concept tests – feasibility study	1					1
Equipment and facility rental service	1			1		
Expert opinion and advisory services	1					1
Foresighting (trends, weak signals, and wild cards)	1					1
Idea selection and testing	1					1
Impact assessment and validation test	1					1
Intake and matching	1			1		
Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	1					1
Legal, regulation, and safety standards support	1					1
Marketing, sales, and networking support	1			1		
Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	1					1
Prototyping test	1					1
Public procurement support services	1					1
Simulation test	1					1
Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	1					1
Stakeholder analysis	1			1	1	1
Usability testing	1					1
(Data) Access management		1			1	
Application evaluation		1		1		
Contract / Consortium Agreement		1		1		
Data analysis		1				1
Data anonymization and pseudonymization		1				1
Data cleaning		1				1
Data governance policy		1			1	
Data management plan		1			1	
Desk / Market research (for project planning purposes)		1		1	1	
Detailed project planning		1			1	

SERVICE NAME	Service type			Process phase		
	R&D	Back-office	Auxiliary	Customer acquisition	Detailed project planning	Project implementation
Dissemination		1				1
Ethical application preparation		1			1	
Fair data compliance process		1				1
Funding call monitoring		1		1		
Grant writing / Preparation		1		1		
Innovation network orchestration		1		1	1	1
IPR management		1			1	1
Living lab project management		1				1
Maintenance		1		1		
Offer preparation		1		1		
Panel management		1				1
Quality and risk management		1				1
Research protocol design		1			1	
Resource allocation		1			1	
Results reporting / Publication writing		1				1
Stakeholder engagement		1				1
Subcontracting negotiation process		1		1		
Temporary research funding		1		1		
Ethics committee review			1		1	
Funding application process			1	1		
Funding call information			1	1		
Research site permit			1		1	

Appendix 2: Living Lab business model elements

BM ELEMENT	ITEM	EXAMPLES
Key activities	Living Lab services	See partners section description
KEY RESOURCES		
Key resources	Funding from project	Grants, fixed funding, investments, and revenues generated from services.
Key resources	Living Lab personnel	1) Living Lab personnel including Living Lab manager, project manager, panel manager, facilitators and researchers, 2) Living Lab hosting organization additional human resources e.g. administration and legal teams, teachers, management team, students who receive salary
Key resources	Living Lab research infrastructure and technologies	1) Physical facilities and campuses, 2) Laboratories and simulations environments, 3) Technological devices and tools, 4) Virtual environments, 5) IT infrastructure.
Key resources	Partners as defined in partners section	See partners section description
Key resources	End-user panels	Access to patients and customers wide range with different diagnosis, living conditions, functionality or similar
Key resources	Non-paid volunteers	1) Bachelor, master or PhD level students or researchers who gain study credits instead of salary, participation is based on educational purpose instead earning a living, 2) Other volunteers having a formal contract
Key resources	Data and publication databases	1) Open and closed access databases such as health care data infrastructure or Living Lab own data generated in projects, 2) Access to scientific publication databases
Key resources	Subcontracted experts	1) Consultants, 2) health care professionals and high level medical personnel, 3) business managers, or similar
Key resources	Living Lab IPR portfolio	Patents and trademarks
Key resources	Standardized processes	1) VITALISE harmonized processes, 2) ISO certified for software production
PARTNERS		
Partners	Local partners	Collaboration partnerships within a one city or municipal or smaller geographical areas such as neighbourhood or city district. Classified based on 1) Academia / Education / Research, 2) Public sector / Policy makers, 3) Industry / Private sector and 4) Civil society
Partners	Regional partners	Collaboration partnerships within a province, a region, or a state which goes beyond single city or municipal, but geographical area is not covering an entire country (e.g. Flanders, Catalunya or Helsinki capital region). Classified based on 1) Academia / Education / Research, 2) Public sector / Policy makers, 3) Industry / Private sector and 4) Civil society.

BM ELEMENT	ITEM	EXAMPLES
Partners	National partners	Collaboration partnerships at the level of an entire country. Classified based on 1) Academia / Education / Research, 2) Public sector / Policy makers, 3) Industry / Private sector and 4) Civil society.
Partners	International and transnational partners	Collaboration partnerships beyond border of one country. Classified based on 1) Academia / Education / Research, 2) Public sector / Policy makers, 3) Industry / Private sector and 4) Civil society.
VALUE PROPOSITION		
Value proposition	Enhanced collaboration and networking possibilities	Opening collaboration and networking possibilities which otherwise would be impossible or hard to gain.
Value proposition	Validity and reliability	Stability and truthfulness of Living Lab process outputs.
Value proposition	Improved innovation	All the different aspects in which the developed solution, whether it be a product, service, process, decision, policy, etc., becomes better due Living Lab process.
Value proposition	Financial and process benefits	The gains that can be expressed in financial terms resulting from the Living Lab innovation process or the improvement of the developed solution.
Value proposition	Benefits for users and society	The impact of Living Lab process outcome to users and society.
Value proposition	Increased skills and capabilities	Improved ability of a person, group, organization, or system to meet its objectives or perform better due Living Lab process outcome.
Value proposition	Safe environment for RDI	Ensuring regulatory and legal compliance, as well as a risk-free area for experimentation, where innovations can be developed and tested
CUSTOMER SEGMENTS		
Customer segments	End user	A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In Living Lab projects, the end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates in research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research. Classification to non-professional and professional users.
Customer segments	Living Lab research infrastructure end user	A person or organization who purchases or uses Living Lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living Lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing Living Lab services and infrastructure. Can be also called to Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases Living Lab services from a Living Lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/ research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups.
CHANNELS		
Channels	Projects	Participating as a partner or coordinator in projects including all project activities.

BM ELEMENT	ITEM	EXAMPLES
Channels	Physical and digital development and testing environments	All real-life (e.g. hospital, outdoors, office, home), laboratory (e.g. simulation lab) and virtual (e.g. game) environments where testing and co-creation is done.
Channels	Direct channels	Direct one-to-one and one-to-many marketing, personal contact network, email, telco, word of mouth)
Channels	Event and conference participation and arrangement	Participating in events, fairs, scientific and professional conferences either as a participant or presenter. Hosting and arranging conferences and events, periodical events for Living Lab innovation ecosystem stakeholders.
Channels	Scientific and professional publications	Publications written by Living Lab personnel to describe Living Lab activities and results to professional and scientific audiences.
Channels	Online, mobile and social media or collaboration platforms.	Web and mobile sites, social media services, youtube and other similar digital media services and collaboration platforms.
Channels	Training courses and education	Degree programs and training courses focusing on Living Lab topics, Internship as a part of studies
Channels	Paid media promotion and marketing	Media campaigns, printed media, PR-activities
Channels	Official public sector channels	Official channel managed by local, regional, national or international public authorities such as funded project databases (e.g. CORDIS).
Channels	Partner channels	Communication in collaboration with Living Lab partner network. See more details in partners section.
Channels	Lobbying and policy channels	Public sector policy and strategy papers and recommendations, advisory meetings, Information meetings with hospitals and administrative
CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS		
Customer relationships	Long-term partnership relations	Partnerships and contacts grounded to promote Living Labs beyond single project e.g. with local authorities, device manufacturers or research sites.
Customer relationships	Project consortium partnerships and collaboration	Project based collaboration relationships based a defined project plan, typically in public funded projects.
Customer relationships	Tailored project, consultation and advisory services via market access	Tailoring Living Lab projects and solutions to meet specific customer needs.
Customer relationships	User communities and stakeholder engagement and orchestration	Engaging with end-users and user communities and other innovation ecosystem stakeholder via workshops, citizen science projects, co-design sessions, and other forms of participatory engagement.

BM ELEMENT	ITEM	EXAMPLES
Customer relationships	Direct personal contacts	email, phone, face-to-face, skype
Customer relationships	Academic partnerships	Joint research activities via research projects, student involvement, knowledge exchange activities, and access to academic expertise and resources.
Customer relationships	Industry collaboration	Industry partners providing funding, expertise, or access to facilities, while Living Labs offer a platform for testing and validating new products, services, or processes in real-world settings.
Customer relationships	Government engagement	Collaboration relationships with local, regional, national and international level to address sustainability challenges, inform policy decisions, and facilitate the adoption of innovative solutions. Government engagement may include co-funding initiatives, regulatory support, access to infrastructure, and participation in pilot projects or demonstration programs.
Customer relationships	Startup and Entrepreneurial Ecosystems	Supporting startups, entrepreneurs, and innovation hubs to develop and commercialize of new ideas and technologies.
Customer relationships	Collaboration with other Living Labs	Collaboration with other local, regional, national or international Living Labs to share best practices, exchange knowledge, and collaborate on cross-cutting research or innovation projects.
Customer relationships	Funding and sponsorship	Relationships with funding organizations, philanthropic foundations, corporate sponsors, or venture capitalists to secure financial support for Living Lab. Also providing funding to SMEs and researcher via open calls.
Customer relationships	Hosting organization internal relationships	Collaboration with hosting organization additional human resources and access to infrastructure.
COST STRUCTURE		
Cost structure	Personnel	All personnel related expenditure including salaries, human resource management, administrative costs, and internship fees. Since personnel are generating the majority of Living Labs costs, the Living Lab service list presented in Table X can be used for evaluating and estimating the operational costs related to personnel. Adding Living Lab personnel roles such as Living Lab manager, researcher, or facilitator as columns will provide an even more focused understanding of cost distribution.
Cost structure	Infrastructure and facilities cost	All facilities, technical environments (rent and investment), equipment, amortisation and depreciation of equipment, (software) licences, utilities costs, common costs, memberships fees and financial costs (interest rate). Classification of Living Lab data collection devices can also act as a tool to keep track of technology-related costs such as license fees or purchase costs.

BM ELEMENT	ITEM	EXAMPLES
Cost structure	R&D development	Software, process, concept, or other similar tools development which are required to run or improve Living Lab activities, own share of external funded projects
Cost structure	Travelling costs	Domestics and international travelling costs
Cost structure	IPR protection fees	Patents and IPR protection
Cost structure	End-user fees and other variable costs relating project activities	Arranging Living Lab activities (e.g. facility rent, food, transportation, insurance), payments for end-user participation, materials and consumables.
Cost structure	Outsourced services and subcontracting costs	ICT infrastructure outsource expenditure (e.g. hosting costs), all other professional service costs e.g. for dissemination purposes (print, graphical design), legal guidance, external experts such as medical doctors.
Cost structure	Marketing, sales and dissemination	Marketing, communication, customer and end-user acquisition costs, engaging users, conference and event participations.
REVENUE STREAMS		
Revenue streams	Public funded project grants	Grants received from local, regional, national and international funding calls such Horizon, Interreg, European Social Fund (ESF). European Regional Development Fund (EARF).
Revenue streams	Fixed funding and annual collaboration contracts/Agreements	Basic funding beyond single project from 1) living owners or hosting organization, 2) local, regional or national authorities.
Revenue streams	Market driven access fees	1) Contracts and invoicing from executing R&D projects (testing and co-creation), 2) consulting and advisory services, 3) recruiting test groups for customers, 4) event participation fees
Revenue streams	Training courses and education fees	1) Training course fees, 2) examination fees, 3) certification fees and 4) site visits to Living Lab.
Revenue streams	Device and infrastructure rental fees	Rental Living Lab equipment and facilities
Revenue streams	In-kind sponsorship	Free of charge equipment provided by technology providers to be used or offered to customers in a dedicated space or for project purposes.
Revenue streams	Donations	Individual or institutional donators
Revenue streams	Royalties	Royalties from IP properties or elsewhere
Revenue streams	Crowdfunding	Reward based crowdfunding (donors can earn rewards based on the amount of money they donate).